

From an EJP SOIL National Hub to a mirror group: example of the French National Hub

Title	From an EJP SOIL National Hub to a mirror group: example of the French hub
Work package no:	1
Description:	Through the French case, this brief report shares a concrete example of how the evolution of an EJP SOIL National Hub can be approached and the questions raised.
Submission date:	30/06/2025
Dissemination level:	PU
Authors:	Flavien Poinçot
Version:	1
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.15769818

Project acronym:	PREPSOIL
Project name:	Preparing for the 'Soil Deal for Europe' Mission
Project number:	101070045
Call topic:	HORIZON-MISS-2021-SOIL-01-01
Type of action:	HORIZON-CSA

**Funded by
the European Union**

Table of content

Aim of this document.....	2
Context.....	3
Approach.....	3
1 st meeting with the National Hub: presenting the concept of Mission Soil Mirror Groups and identifying first recommendations and concerns.....	4
2 nd meeting with the National Hub: official proposal and practical discussion on the organization .	4
Conclusion.....	5
Agendas of the two meetings	6
First meeting: March, 2024 14 th , 10:00-16:30	6
Second meeting: May, 2024, 12 th , 10:00 – 16:30	7

Aim of this document

This document shares feedback on two meetings organized in France to establish a Mission Soil Mirror Group building on the EJP SOIL National Hub. The objective is to share a concrete example of a country building on its National Hub to develop its Mirror Group and the topics discussed with the stakeholders. This document is produced as part of PREPSOIL actions related to the establishment and development of Mission Soil Mirror Groups. For more information about existing Mirror Groups in Europe and how they work, please read PREPSOIL report “Mission Soil Mirror Groups: where do we stand?” (10.5281/zenodo.15753898).

HORIZON-MISS-2021-SOIL-01-01 /
Preparing the ground for healthy soils:
Building capacities for engagement, outreach and knowledge
PREPSOIL – 2022-2025

Context

The EJP SOIL French National Hub is built on a previously existing network, the French network of scientific and technical expertise on soils (RNEST). The network has brought together stakeholders from academia, policy makers, companies, farmer organizations, and other actors working on soils (forest, agricultural, urban, industrial fallow land, contaminated sites, natural areas, etc.). It is supported by organizations representing national soil RDI key stakeholders: the French ministries in charge of agriculture, environment, and higher education and research, co-chairing the network, three national agencies, a research institute, a learned society, and two agricultural organizations. The RNEST also relies on an Expert Committee composed of 26 experts with varied and complementary expertise profiles (pedology, hydrology, law, etc.), and diverse sectors of activity (academic research, consultancy firm, association, etc.).

When EJP SOIL established the National Hubs, the RNEST became the embryo for the development of the French Hub, with three additional organizations invited to join to strengthen the representation of stakeholders from the agricultural sector.

With the hub working well and its composition appropriate for the construction of a mirror group, ministries considered building on this group to establish the French Mirror Group.

Approach

Following dialogues at the ministry level, where representatives from ministries agreed on the need for a Mirror Group and the relevance of building on the National Hub and RNEST, two meetings were organized in 2024 and 2025 with the French National Hub.

The first meeting aimed at consulting the members on their views regarding their role and possible involvement in the Mirror Group, and on possible additional stakeholders that could be invited to join the group.

The second meeting was organized to present a formal proposal from the ministries, based on the previous discussions, as well as highlights from PREPSOIL overview of Mirror Group establishment in Europe. The objective was to achieve a common agreement on how the Mirror Group would operate, based on the proposal from the Ministries and opinions and recommendations of the participants.

This approach is in line with the recommendations from PREPSOIL guidelines (<https://zenodo.org/records/12097401>), with ministries first aligning their expectations and agreeing on a process, and then consulting the National Hubs to identify additional stakeholders and discuss with them the purpose of the Mirror Group and how it could work.

Although the guidelines were produced to foster the expansion of EJP SOIL National Hub into Soil Health National Hubs, the overall recommended method is still relevant for the establishment of a Soil Mission Mirror Group from a National hub or any already existing network.

HORIZON-MISS-2021-SOIL-01-01 /
Preparing the ground for healthy soils:
Building capacities for engagement, outreach and knowledge
PREPSOIL – 2022-2025

[1st meeting with the National Hub: presenting the concept of Mission Soil Mirror Groups and identifying first recommendations and concerns](#)

To foster participation in an in-person meeting and avoid stakeholder fatigue, the first meeting was organized jointly with EJP SOIL, in March 2024. Regarding the mirror group dynamic, the objective of this meeting was to share information about the expectations towards the future mirror group, the recommendations from the Mission Soil Board, and gather feedback, recommendations and possible concerns from the National Hub.

In addition to the questions and discussion following the presentation related to Mirror Groups, a time for discussion was set towards the end of the meeting, after updates on the RNEST and the National Hub activities, so the members would have a complete overview of their ongoing or future actions and could envisage how this would articulate with the activities of a Mirror Group.

Overall, there was a general agreement as to the relevance of a mirror group or the interest of building on the hub. The main points of discussion in relation to the establishment of the French Mirror Group were related to:

- Missing stakeholders in the current configuration of the group;
- How might the creation of the Mirror Group affect the Hub's current activities and priorities, and would this require greater commitment from members
- The status of the members nominated in the Mirror group, meaning their role as representatives. Within RNEST, and therefore the EJP SOIL National Hub, most stakeholders involved are part of an expert group, where members are nominated *intuitu personae*, which means they are nominated for their expertise within their field of activities. They share their own recommendations, and do not represent any organization. In the mirror group, however, it was initially expected to have stakeholders representing their organizations. In this case, each stakeholder would need to be mandated by their organization and, when consulted, may possibly need to organize specific internal consultations to elaborate their organization's official position.

Consequently, the main outcomes from the meeting were the identification of new relevant stakeholders to invite, as well as two key aspects to further explore before forming the Mirror Group: the time required for members to participate in the Mirror Group, and the exact roles and representation of each member within the mirror group.

[2nd meeting with the National Hub: official proposal and practical discussion on the organization](#)

The second meeting was organized in May 2025, to allow PREPSOIL to share some highlights regarding the overview of Mirror group establishment in Europe. Stakeholders identified in the previous meeting were invited to participate.

The main objective of the meeting was to present an official proposal from the ministries, and refined the suggested organization of the Mirror Group based on feedback from the stakeholders as well as examples from PREPSOIL overview.

To encourage in-person participation, the meeting was organized as a joint meeting focusing on national hub expansion into a mirror group in the morning, and specific actions and national initiatives from RNEST and its Expert Committee in the afternoon.

The main outcome of the meeting was the discussion and decision related to the establishment of the French Mirror Group. Some concerns were raised by the participants regarding the possibility that conflicts of interest may arise when participating in the Mirror Group, especially when sharing recommendations in relation to EU or national funding opportunities and synergies at the national level. This shows that it is relevant to establish and communicate clear procedures to avoid such conflicts when establishing a Mirror Group, and to explain and be transparent with the rules and the scope of the Group.

Discussions on the organizational process and the frequency of the meetings allowed stakeholders to share their own experiences, preferences and possible concerns, and new possible stakeholders were suggested, who could bring complementary perspective to the current configuration of the group.

At the end of the session, the group decided to work as a Mirror Group with a new organizational process, for a one-year test run. After this one year, the group will reflect on the past actions and organization, and possibly adjust.

For this first configuration, the mirror group will be built on a small number of stakeholders that will form the equivalent of a policy group representing key national organizations from research and innovation, as well as national authorities and national funding agencies that could foster the implementation of national, regional or local actions. The other stakeholders will be involved as part of a stakeholder group whose members are named *intuitu personae*, that will be consulted by the policy group and that will share their own expertise without representing their organization.

The next steps are the official nomination of each member of the Mirror Group and the planification of the first meeting that would likely happen in the autumn 2025.

Conclusion

When building on an EJP SOIL National Hub to establish a mirror group, it is necessary to involve the National Hub in the creation process and to plan dedicated time for discussion. The topics discussed, the concerns and challenges raised, and the recommendations are of course dependent on the national context.

However, this example shows that discussions are needed even with well-established hubs. While having such hubs facilitates the establishment of a Mirror Group, the process may still need several steps. This shows that it is important to clearly define the roles, but also the status of the members involved in Mirror Group, as well as a clear articulation with the work done in the network or the group it builds on.

The solution adopted in this case, with a dedicated time to test an organizational arrangement, may be a useful example for other countries as it allows to progress despite remaining uncertainties and to easily make adjustments within the organizational process if needed.

HORIZON-MISS-2021-SOIL-01-01 /
Preparing the ground for healthy soils:
Building capacities for engagement, outreach and knowledge
PREPSOIL – 2022-2025

Agendas of the two meetings

First meeting: March, 2024 14th, 10:00-16:30

MORNING (10:00-12:30)

9:30 – *Welcoming participants (welcome coffee)*

10:00 – Opening

Introduction to the day, presentation of the agenda and introduction to the first item.

10:10 – EJP SOIL Workshop: How can we how can we improve the dissemination and appropriation of knowledge for soil management and protection?

Organised by EJP SOIL. Presentation of the results of an EJP SOIL survey and participatory workshop to gather feedback and suggestions from the stakeholders.

11:50 – Mirror Groups and National Hubs: what are the expectations from the European and National level? How can we build on what is already in place?

- *Brief reminder of the history of the French National Hub.*
- *Brief presentation of the concept of Mirror Groups as defined by the Mission Soil Board and the articulation with PREPSOIL initial objective to build Soil Health National Hub.*
- *Presentation by the Ministries of the national context and specific expectations towards the future Mirror Group, as well as recommendations from the Mission Soil Board.*
- *Presentation of a possible organisation and possible challenges, to be discussed later during the day.*

AFTERNOON (13:45-16:30)

13:45 –Presentation of a French initiative in relation to soil health assessment at the local level for information and feedback.

14:20 –Information session

Session to share updates on the actions completed and in progress, as well as information on recent policy news and EU initiatives.

Opportunity to share information both from the stakeholders and the ministries on various soil-related actions and initiatives. PREPSOIL knowledge hub was advertised as well as the coming Mobile App.

14:50 – Breakout Session

Organised as a plenary session. This time was mainly focused on reactions and discussions about the involvement of the National Hub in the future Mirror Group, missing stakeholders and the challenges that could arise.

15:50 – Break

16:00 – Synthesis, future actions and conclusion of the day

Discussion and planification of future actions based on the information of the day and conclusion.

HORIZON-MISS-2021-SOIL-01-01 /
Preparing the ground for healthy soils:
Building capacities for engagement, outreach and knowledge
PREPSOIL – 2022-2025

Second meeting: May, 2024, 12th, 10:00 – 16:30

MORNING (10:00-12:30)

9:30 – *Welcoming participants online and in-person*

10:00 – Opening

Introduction to the day, presentation of the agenda and introduction to the first item.

10:05 – Introduction of the participants

Each participant takes the floor for a brief introduction as this meeting gathered new stakeholders, beyond RNEST and the EJP SOIL National Hub

10:35 – Context and initiative

Presentation of the EU context and the role of the ministries' representatives leading the establishment of the French Mirror Group, presentation of the initiative and the history of the French National Hub, presentation of the official proposal to establish the French Mirror Group.

10:55 – Mission Soil Mirror Groups, where do the Member States stand?

Presentation of PREPSOIL and its work related to the support of Mirror Group establishment and development in Europe. Highlight of key results from PREPSOIL's overview of the current establishment of Mirror Groups in Europe, to foster the coming discussion with the participants.

11:10 – Presentation of Mission Board member Muriel Mambrini

11:25 – Q&A and discussion on the presentations

11:45 – Informative session on Horizon Europe

Information session on Horizon Europe opened calls, contact points and national initiatives to support potential applicants

12:00 – Discussions on the mirror group proposal

Discussion on the proposal from the ministries (organisation, working methods, stakeholders invited)

12:50 – Lunch break

AFTERNOON (14:00-16 :00)

The afternoon was dedicated to actions specific to the Expert Committee of RNEST.

14:00 – Information on the completed and ongoing work of the RNEST expert committee

14:10 – Focus on an ongoing action: organisation of a French session at Remtech Europe

14:20 – Discussion and definition of future actions

Future actions were discussed based on the French context, information shared in the morning (in relation also with the role of the Committee within the Mirror Group activities), and latest news (legislation in preparation at the national level, recent initiative from a stakeholder targeting policymakers and land managers).

15:25 – Breakout sessions

The participants further discuss the actions identified earlier and defined the next steps

16h05 – Back in plenary: reporting on the breakout session

16h20 – Wrap-up, next steps and conclusion